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Śrī Jagannāth and Vaiṣṇavism

Dr.Nilachal Mishra¹

Abstract

India is renowned for its culture, heritage, tradition, and Philosophy in this World. And India is very popular for its spiritual wisdom and is full of differential works and the temple of Lord Jagannātha is one of the wonderful creations also. A place like Puri is very famous for car festivals (Ratha Yātrā) in the whole World. Puruṣottam Kṣhetra is a pious place and it is looked at in Ṛg Veda and the Mahābhārata. Puri is known as Śrī Kṣhetra, Nīlādri, and Puruṣottama Puri. The impression of Trinity like Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Maheśvara has been shown in the reflection of the Jagannātha cult. The three Hindu sects as Vaiṣṇavism, Śaivism, and Śaktism are found in the temple of Śrī Jagannātha also. Śrī Jagannātha has been worshiped as Dāru Brahma with the beliefs of different types of Hindu sects. But He is the Lord of the entire Universe. His concept was accepted by thousands of devotees, not only in India but also all over the World. The present paper defines the Cult of Jagannātha from many aspects and about the Viṣṇu devotees briefly.

Keywords

Lord, Jagannātha, Viṣṇu, Culture, Worship.

Introduction

Vaiṣṇavism reflects the life of Viṣṇu bhaktas who pray to lord viṣṇu in his all forms like Rāma, Krishna, Nṛsimha, Nārāyaṇa, Śrīnivaśa, and Lord Jagannātha as the supreme deity and the Lord of this world. The Hindus are divided into many sects as per worshiping of the Vedic deities. These sects also crossed the normal caste division as per varṇāśrama. The sects are like Brāhmaṇas, Kṣhatriyas, Vaiśhyas, and Śūdras. The Vedic Civilization was gradually involved with the thoughts of the Vedantins which were completely Metaphysics. They

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confess the reality of Ātmā, and which is the same as Brahman. That Brahman or God who lives in every being. The Brahman or God is known as omniscient, omnipresent, and omnipotent. All the living beings are one of the parts of him. This creation is the handwork of Brahman or God. God looks in all the movable and immovable parts of the Universe. The different types of Hindu sects worshiped different Vedic Gods.

Ādi Śaṅkarācārya tried to unite the Hinduism and established the Sanatan dharma. He recognized the different major schools like Vaiṣṇavism, Shaivism, Sauram, Kaumaram and etc. Ādi Śaṅkarācārya completed the worship of panchayatana. (Satapathy 121-22)

Lord Jagannātha is the main God of Puri. Due to the temple of Lord Jagannātha, Puri is a well-known and very famous City in this World. Among the four dhāmas, Śrī Jagannātha dhām is one of them. Śrī Jagannātha called Puruṣottama and His place Puri is also renowned Puruṣottama Kṣhetra, Śaṅkha Kṣhetra, Śrī Kṣhetra, etc. Śrī Jagannātha and the place of Puri mentioned in many Purāṇas like Skanda Purāṇa, Nārada Purāṇa, Padma Purāṇa, Śiva Purāṇa, Utkal Māhātmya, Deulatola of Nilambar Das. (Pradhan 82)

As per Bṛhat Narasimha Purāṇa Śrī Jagannātha place is the only pious place in this creation which is called Puruṣottama, and this place is the heaven on this earth, and God's desire to see it. (Pradhan) Regarding the piousness of the place Śiva Purāṇa says the place is like puruṣottama known as the very pious place on this soil, and that can give the salvation to the living beings. This place is a very unique place where the Supreme Lord of this Universe exists in a timber appearance (Pradhan).

Vaiṣṇavism is different from others

Among the Viṣṇu devotees, there are no caste differences, so it is said 'Vaiṣṇava Jātivudhī' such type of devotees has no sorrows, so it is said 'saṭhamaitrupayati yorthatruṣṇām tamadhamaceṣṭhamavehi nāsyā bhaktam'. In Bhakti Yoga, the Bhagavad-gītā says the real devotees of God, and this scripture describes the two categories of Vaiṣṇavas like this. 'Vaiṣṇavāḥ dvidiāḥ proktāḥ bāhyā ābhyantarsthā'. The sage, Narasimha from the State of Gujarat sang the song of a vaiṣṇava like this.

‘Vaiṣṇava jane to tene kahiye jo paraye jane re’

The Vaiṣṇavas are unique and they can realize the sorrows of others. This song was very impressive to Gandhi, and Mahatma Gandhi sang this song in his prayer frequently (Satapathy 129).

Lord Jagannātha is the Supreme Soul

The Vedas, Upaniṣads and many Purāṇas have been described Lord Jagannātha and Lord Krishna as the same and there is no difference between them. Saint Kabir visited Śrīmandira and He saw Krishna had given Him darshan after leaving His sit from Mathurā. In Gītā, Lord Krishna says there are the two types of Puruṣa in this World one is Kṣhara, and other is Akṣhara. Further, God declares that He is the beyond of the Kṣhara and Akṣhara puruṣa. So He is the Supreme Soul means Puruṣottama in this creation. The description of Gītā is as follows:

Dvāvimaou puruṣau loke kṣaraścākṣara eva ca/

Kṣarasarvāṇi bhūtāni kuṭasthokṣara ucyate//

Yasmāt kṣaramatitoham akṣarādapi cottamaḥ/

Atosmi loke vede ca prathitaḥ puruṣottamaḥ// (Prabhupada 525)

Lord Jagannātha is called Parambrahma and is established as DāruBrahma(made in wood), and He worshiped as Jagannātha at Puruṣottama Kṣhetra, Puri. The worship of the Lord Jagannātha has been performed as per human philosophy like ‘Yathā dehe tathā deve’, and the man looks like in the shape of God. The rituals and festivals of the Lord Jagannātha have performed as the same as human beings, and which are very distinctive and exceptional (Dash and Mishra 15-16).

Vaiṣṇavism’ this word comes from the word Viṣṇu. The person who worships Viṣṇu called Vaiṣṇava. The worshiping of such type of practice is called Vaiṣṇavism. In this regard, religious works are not compulsory. But the feelings of God like Rādhā and Krishna are only necessary. The bhakti of Rādhā and Krishna is not different from a human. In this feeling, there is no separation between God and humans (Khuntia 65-66). Bhagavān says I do not reside in Vaikuntha, and not in the heart of the Sages. But where my devotees pray to me that place is my living place. The description is like this-

‘Mad bhaktāḥ yatra gyānti tatra tiṣṭhāmi Nārada’ (Satapathy 129)

The Rāmāyaṇa of Vāmiki described Śrī Jagannātha has taken birth as Śrī Rāma (Satapathy 132). The Bhagavad-gītā also describes Lord Jagannāth incarnated himself to save the earth from unrighteousness and misdeeds of the wicked fellows. In Gītā, Bhagavān says:

Yadā Yadā hi dharmasya glānirbhavati bhārata/
 Abhyuthānamadharmasya tadātmānaṃ sṛjāmyaham//
 Paritrāṇāya sādḥūnām vināśāya ca duskṛtām/
 Dharma saṁsthāpanārthāya sambhavāmi yuge yuge//

(Prabhupada 167-69)

The special qualities of Śrī Kṣhetra

In Purṣottam Kṣhetra, and in the temple of the Lord Jagannātha, the three idols like Śrī Jagannātha, brother Balabhadra, and Devī Subhadrā, Bhuvanesvarī, Sheetalā, Lakṣmī, Bimalā, Gāyatrī, Bātamangalā, Sarasvatī, Bata Ganesha worshiped in the main temple premises of the Lord Jagannātha. Besides this, there are Rohiṇī Kuṇḍa, and Vatavṛkṣha worshiped also. The Vatavṛkṣha possess great quality and also have the power to fulfill all desires of the devotees.

In the cult of Lord Jagannātha, the people think Śrī Jagannātha is the supreme God of this World, and other deities take the power from him. The prasād of the Lord Jagannātha is called Mahāprasād and it became very pious after offering it before Devī Vimalā. The Mahāprasād is also known as Abhadā between the devotees. And after surrendering it became famous as Nirmālya and that can be kept for long days by the Viṣṇu devotees also (Satapathy 132-133).

Goddess Suhadrā is Aparāśakti and Balabhadra is Paraśakti

The Rathayātrā of Lord Jagannātha is unique and very famous not only in India but also all over the world. Śrī Jagannātha existed in Ratnasimhāsana with all other forms like Parāśakti and Aparāśakti which is described in the Bhagavad-gītā as follows:

Bhūmirāponalo vāyuḥ evaṁ mano bhudireva ca/
 Ahaṁkāra iti yaṁ bhināprakṛtiraṣṭadhā//
 Apareyamitastvanyām prakṛtiṁ vidhi me parām/
 Jīvabhūtām mahābāho yayedam dhāryate Jagat//

(Prabhupada B G. VIIIk- 4-5)

Goddess Subhadrā identifies Aparāśakti, and Śrī Balabhadra recognizes Parāśakti, and Lord Jagannātha is narrated Paramātmā (supreme soul) in various Upaniṣads. He has no legs and hands but is easy to attain. The description is like this. 'Apāṇipādo Javano grahitā' (Satapathy 135).

The devotion of the devotees of Lord Jagannātha

Śrī Caitanya Mahāprabhu and the poet Jayadeva are the two great devotees of Lord Jagannātha. The childhood name of Śrī Caitanya was Nimai Pandita, and after taking sanyāsa, He became known as Caitanya Mahāprabhu between the Viṣṇu devotees. He visited for 45 years many places for his spiritual activities. He disappeared at Puri in 1455. He lived in Navadvīpa as a scholar and married to Lakṣhmīpriyā, who died at an early age. After the death of his wife, He left home. And after some days, He accepted Śrīmatī Viṣṇupriyā as his second wife by the request of his mother.

Caitanya Mahāprabhu lived in Puri for 24 years and He accepted Puri as His main residing place at the request of his mother. And He accepted the uttering of the name of God is the best and ultimate path for getting salvation in this Kali Yuga. So, He says:-

Harenāma Harenāma Harenāmaiva Kevalam

Kalau Nāsti Eva Nāsti Eva Gatiranyathā// (Satapathy 181-189)

Likely Caitanya Mahāprabhu, the poet Jayadeva was also regarded as the best devotee of Lord Jagannātha. He wrote the Khaṇḍa Kāvya Gītagovinda, that story based on the love story of Rādhā and Krishna with very sweet and soft voices. The description of the poet is as follows:

Yadi Haris maraṇe sarasaṁ mano Yadi vilāsakalāsu kutūhalam/

Madhurakomala kānta padāvaliṁ Sṛṇu tadā Jayadeva sarasvatim//

(Sarma and Sharma 10)

And further, it is described by the poet like this.

Yadgāndharvakalāsu kauśalamanudhyānaṁ Ca yad Vaiṣṇavaṁ,

Yacchṛṅgāravivekatattva racanākāvyeṣu lilāyitam/

Tatsarvaṁ jayadevapaṇḍitakaveḥ Kṛṣṇaikatānātmaḥ,

Dṛśānandāḥ parisodhayantu sudhiyaḥ śrīgītagovindatataḥ//

(Sarma and Sharma 403)

The implementation of music in the Kāvya, Gītagovinda shows a new look towards the cultural and historical study of Sanskrit literature. The devotional song of the Gītagovinda Kāvya like 'pralaya payodhi jale dhṛtavānasi vedam' has been described in Malva and that can exceed the Moha Mudgara of Shankara (Satapathy 76).

Conclusion

From the above discussions, it is concluded that Jagannātha culture is only one culture where the devotee and God are the same in every ritual and social customs, and daily works. Lord Jagannātha is the paramātmā (supreme soul) and He has the power to control the whole Universe. There is no difference in caste, creed, and religion in Jagannātha culture. He came to the Badadanda to give the darshan for all in every year where every person can get his darshan without any caste differences. He is the knower of the inner hearts. So, he is called Antaryāmī, Chakākshi, Jagannātha, etc. He is the Nātha or Svāmī of all devotees. Who is able to disappear all the obstacles and sorrows of his devotees without any type of condition. So, it is said by someone like this.

Vetti saṁsāraduḥkhāni dadāti sukhamavyam/

Tasmāddārumayaṁ brahma vedānteṣūpāgiyate// (Satapathy 155)

He is Līlāmaya and the Lord of the Universe. And He is known as 'patitapāvana' to all. He is the soul of all Hindus. He is the beyond of present, past, and future. And He is the main worshipful God for us and Hinduism unconditionally.

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